

Mist Netting of Bats on Tuckernuck Island, Nantucket, MA
August-October 2011

A Report to Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative
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Abstract: I used mist nets to sample bats on 12 nights, 12 August to 24 September 2011 in order to address how many migratory bats cross Nantucket Sound during the fall. There are no resident bats on Tuckernuck (pers. obs.), so any bats caught there have presumably just flown across the Sound. I opened mist nets on 12 nights 12 August to 24 September, and caught a total of 3 Red Bats (*Lasiurus borealis*), all on two nights in August. This was a smaller number of bats than anticipated, but I don't think I was missing bats that were present. I saw many fewer bats in 2011 than I did in 2012, using just casual observations.

Introduction

Interest in bats that migrate across Nantucket Sound is elevated now because of the potential threat posed by wind turbines likely to be erected in Nantucket Sound and elsewhere in the general area (Kunz et al. 2007, Cryan and Brown 2007). Yet there is relatively little information available on the species that migrate across the Sound on a regular basis and their abundance during migration periods. Many anecdotal observations, including my own at Tuckernuck Island, indicate that fair numbers (up to 100+ bats seen in one night at Tuckernuck) of bats regularly appear on the islands in Nantucket Sound during late August and early September, and probably in smaller numbers during the spring as well (Miller 1897, David and Hitchcock 1965, Broders et al. 2003). My goal was to use mist nets to sample migratory bats at Tuckernuck during August and September 2011 to **1.)** Document which species are present and **2.)** Obtain estimates of relative abundance of the species.

Figure 1.) Red Bat in mist net. One of two (adult and young) captured 19 August 2011,

Methods and Results

I used Polyester mist nets designed specifically for bats by Avinet (Dryden, NY; www.avinet.com). They have 38 mm mesh and measure 2.6 m high and 12 m long. Compared to similar nets used for catching birds, the pouches between trammels are smaller so there is less net in which to get tangled. I usually set 5 nets (range 1-6) each evening. The number was that I thought that I could effectively check while working alone. I wanted to avoid being inundated with bats and creating a situation in which I could not disentangle them fast enough. I opened the nets at sunset or shortly thereafter, and closed them after 3 hours or so. In my past experience I have had the highest capture rates in the first half hour or so after dark. I chose places to erect nets based on where I have seen bats foraging before, and also near natural “tunnels”, such as where the dirt roads enter the forest, as such places tend to force the bats to fly at net height (2.6 m). I set all the nets near the center of the island, near the Suzie Robinson and Peter Watrous houses.

I was vaccinated against rabies in June and July 2011 (3 vaccinations), so as to be prepared in the event of bites. I wore Kevlar or leather gloves whenever handling bats, and was not bitten during the course of the study.

I checked all nest every 30-45 minutes. In between checking, I walked the area and searched for bats against the sky. On several nights, I saw a few bats flying about at dusk, but never anywhere near as many as the 100 or so that I saw in early September 2010.

I caught a total of 3 Red Bats during the entire project (Table 1).

Discussion

There were two obvious findings from this bout of mist netting in the fall of 2011 at Tuckernuck Island. First, I caught a surprisingly small number of bats, given that I had seen at least 100 bats in one night during September 2010. The numbers of migrant bats reaching Tuckernuck is likely episodic, as are the numbers of migratory birds (that is very large numbers on some nights interspersed with many nights on which none occur), but even so, it seems that I sampled on enough nights and during the appropriate conditions to have caught more individuals. Second, I only caught one species, Red Bat. Red Bats are indeed the most frequently identified bat species at Tuckernuck and they seem to occur over a greater range of dates than other species. However, numbers of bats that I have seen in early fall, during 2010, as well as during other years, include a large proportion of what look like *Myotis* species due to their small size, and other studies (e.g. Broders et al. 2003) suggest that *Myotis* should be among the most numerous migrant bats found at coastal localities in fall.

I do not think that large numbers of species other than Red Bat were present and that I just failed to catch them. I saw few bats in 2011, and those that I did see appeared to be large, close to the size of Red Bat, and I suspect that they were all in fact, this species. The one time that I clearly saw one bat that was clearly smaller than another with which it was flying was immediately before I caught an adult and immature Red Bat together in a net on 19 August.

Therefore it is my conclusion that bats were relatively scarce on Tuckernuck during fall 2011. The *Myotis* species have been strongly impacted by White Nose disease (http://www.batconservation.org/drupal/white-nose?gclid=CK-n-_Gqv68CFUGo4Aod6Bb_yA) and perhaps part of their scarcity at Tuckernuck in 2011 is related to mortality from this disease and consequent population decline.

Table 1. Bats caught by mist net, and mist-netting effort at Tuckernuck Island, Nantucket, MA. Fall 2011.

Date	Number of Nets	Times	Bats Captured	Bats Seen		
12 August	1	2000-2200	0	6		
19 August	4	1945-2400	2 Red Bats	0		
20 August	5	1945-2200	0	1		
23 August	5	1945-0030	0	2		
24 August	5	2000-2330	1 Red Bat	1		
26 August	5	1945-0030	0	0		
2 September	6	2000-2400	0	0	1 woodcock caught	
3 September	5	2000-2400	0	2 Red Bats		
4 September	5	1915-2330	0	1-2 Red Bats		
11 September	5	2000-2200	0	0	1 woodcock caught; 3 seen	
17 September	5	1930-2230	0	3-4		
24 September	5	1900-2200	0	1		

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